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Fifth-Generation/Hybrid Warfare and Its Implications in Pakistan

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Abstract

Everything that affects one's mind against some religion, culture, moral values, state, and security forces is called 5th-generation war, and Pakistan is a victim of it. In terms of Security Alliances, Nuclear Power, and Geo-Strategic location, Pakistan possesses prime importance on the globe. Anti-Pakistan powers, by using 5th-

generation warfare tools, have concocted various issues for Pakistan's national integration, such as security, terrorism, ethnic issues, and socio-economic problems. This monograph report aims to analyze fifth-generation warfare and its challenges to Pakistan. In the modern era, wars are not declared or waged conventionally: instead, it is instigated by clandestine agents using military, non-military, media, cyber tools, information operations, NGOs, non-state actors, intelligence agencies, propaganda, economic tools, insurgency, and terrorism. The adversaries have been waging FGW against Pakistan for a long time. Pakistan became a nuclear power in 1998 and declared that conventional battle remains very hard for adversaries. Hence, they are using tools of fifth-generation warfare against Pakistan to destabilize it internally and achieve their nefarious designs. The enemies are behind conspiracies to destabilize Pakistan internally and undermine its image in the global community, sponsoring, financing, and training terrorists to conduct covert operations within Pakistan's territory. The enemies have been spreading propaganda, misleading reports, and false news to damage the national unity of Pakistan. They are trying to influence international institutions, particularly the FATF, to portray Pakistan as a terrorist sponsoring state. Pakistan is being subjected to fifth-generation warfare massively. This research paper highlights the challenges of FGW Pakistan is presently facing.

Keywords: Fifth-Generation Warfare (FGW), National Security, Propaganda and Information Warfare, Pakistan, Socio-Economic Destabilization

JEL Classification: F52, H56, D74, O53, Z18

Introduction

The 21st century has witnessed the beginning of a new social, political, economic, and technological advancement. The nature of warfare has also

changed in the modern world. In the present era, the internet and information technology have changed the nature of warfare. The role of the internet is growing in the realm of warfare. The Internet is the main tool used in the latest generation of warfare. The latest generation of warfare is the battle of perception and information. It is waged when it becomes impossible for a state to destroy its rival state through direct military attack. Hence, propaganda, disinformation, the use of non-state actors, and media campaigns are launched to generate anarchy, chaos, and resentment. Media campaigns are out of proportion and beyond the control of a state. The rise of social media has led to new trends in the domain of warfare. Social media tools, particularly Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram, and Twitter, have become instruments of fifth-generation warfare. Fake news, misleading reports, and falsified propaganda are spread through these modern media tools. (Azad, 2020).

Pakistan has a significant geopolitical location. It has always played a positive role at the regional and global level. It has great importance among world powers due to its geo-strategic location, nuclear capability, relation with rising superpower China, and the initiation of CPEC. Hence, it is facing threats from the latest generation of warfare, waged by hostile intelligence agencies. The adversaries are waging this type of warfare against Pakistan to create chaos and uncertainty in the country and are trying to disrupt the internal security of the country with the tools of hybrid warfare. Since Pakistan became a nuclear power in 1998, its enemies have been unable to launch any form of conventional battle against it. Hence, waging a hybrid war against Pakistan has become a preferred strategy by adversaries. Addressing a ceremony marking Defense Day at the General Headquarters (GHQ) in Rawalpindi, General Bajwa stated Pakistan is facing many challenges aimed at discrediting the country and its defense forces.

“We are facing the challenge that has been imposed on us in the form of the fifth-generation or hybrid war. Its purpose is to discredit the country and its defense forces and spread chaos”, he said. “We are well aware of this danger. We will surely succeed in winning this war with the cooperation of the nation.” (Yasin, 2020) . The enemies are trying hard to disrupt the internal security of the country by using electronic, print, and social media, NGOs, disgruntled elements, and other means as tools of fifth-generation warfare. Anti-Pakistan elements are engaged in inciting sectarianism in Pakistani society.

Fifth-generation warfare undertaken by adversaries against Pakistan has multiple negative impacts, which include social unrest, ethnic and sectarian divisions, defamation of Pakistan globally, economic unrest, and many more. Pakistan is making efforts to counter the nefarious agenda of the enemy by preparing itself for fifth-generation warfare. This research

paper highlights challenges of fifth-generation warfare to Pakistan, which include propaganda war, media campaigns, externally-abetted terrorism, etc. The study explores “Fifth-generation Warfare and its Challenges for Pakistan”. In this study, the researcher focuses on media, economy, cultural war, and sectarianism, which are being used as tools of fifth-generation warfare against Pakistan. For this research, data have been collected through both primary and secondary sources of data collection. Different data collection tools have been used to conduct this research. Using primary sources, the researcher conducted interviews with media persons and security officials to get relevant and necessary data for this research. Using secondary sources, the researcher used books, scholarly articles, research journals, official reports, and newspapers to gather relevant data for this research.

Propaganda Campaigns against Pakistan: Building Misperceptions

The last two decades witnessed rising trends of propaganda campaigns against Pakistan. Pakistan is being subjected to hybrid warfare through Non-Kinetic resources. India has formed a nexus with Israel and the US and is influencing the international media. Mearsheimer and Stephen explain that pro-Israel organizations work hard to influence the media, think tanks, and academia, because these institutions are critical in shaping popular opinion. (Mearsheimer, 2006). The media campaigns launched against Pakistan aim to distort its image at the global level and destabilize it. India is enjoying its leverage over international media to build misperceptions against Pakistan. Indeed, India is pursuing its nefarious goals to damage Pakistan’s image at the global level. India is trying to build a perception that Pakistan is an unsafe place and is sponsoring militancy in the region. An extensive Indian network of fake NGOs and think tanks was exposed in 2019, which was found responsible for operating more than 200 fake news outlets to influence the European Union (EU) and the United Nations (UN) to distort Pakistan’s image at the global level. (G. Machado, 2020).

Furthermore, the Indian and the international media associations are engaged in spreading negative propaganda, false news, misinformation, and unjustified criticism to build a misperception about Pakistan to weaken its position in the international community. The West and India are using all means, including non-traditional and non-kinetic resources, to push Pakistan towards a difficult political and economic position. Realizing the fact of hybrid warfare challenges being faced by Pakistan, Army Chief Gen. Qamar Bajwa in 2018 stated that, We are now confronting hybrid conflict where focus is shifting to subversion on religious, sectarian, ethnic, and social issues. (Maqbool, 2018)

Role of Social Media

The twenty-first century has seen the emerging role of media technology and the internet. The rise of social media, along with fast internet technologies, has changed the world. Social media tools such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and WhatsApp have become favorite sources of information. (Ortiz-Ospina, 2019). There is no denying the fact that social media has brought positive changes in the world, but on the other hand, it has become an effective tool to spread fake news, misleading reports, and propaganda.

Social media is being used as an instrument of warfare (Dr Farah Naz, 2020). Anti-Pakistan forces are using social media tools to spread fake news and misinformation against Pakistan. According to an estimation in 2008, there were about 326 million people who used social media in India. This large number of social media consumers mainly receive fake news and misinformation from the Indian government, which they spread with no justification. After the Pulwama attack in February 2019, the Indian government promoted false news and misinformation to the public (Azad, 2020). The Indian government even said that the Indian Air Force had shot down a Pakistani F-16, which was never proven. In addition, India also failed to prove its claim of killing militants inside Pakistan's territory (Yasin, 2020). The Indian national media, sponsored by the Indian government, has always been involved in such kind by false reporting.

Propaganda Campaigns Against Pakistan's Nuclear Weapons

Pakistan is a responsible nuclear power. After India became a nuclear power, it became inevitable for Pakistan to become a nuclear state and deter the hostile intentions of India and maintain a balance of power in the region. When Pakistan successfully tested nuclear weapons in 1998 and got the status of a nuclear state, unjustifiable criticism followed by a propaganda campaign started against it. The United States and the Western world perceived Pakistan's nuclear capability as an alarming trend. They launched propaganda campaigns and tried to pressure Pakistan. They labelled Pakistan an unsafe and unstable country. The reports highlighted by the US and Western world were based on probabilistic estimations with no reasonable ground.

After the event of September 11, 2001, propaganda against Pakistan's nuclear assets intensified. The international media is trying to build a misperception about Pakistan's nuclear weapons programme. The international media, along with think tanks, nuclear experts, and main Western politicians, promoted biased, negative criticism and propaganda against Pakistan's nuclear status. In September 2001, the Institute for Science and International Security (ISIS) raised concerns that Pakistan's nuclear weapons could fall into the hands of terrorists (ISIS, 2001).

Furthermore, in April 2004, the European Union (EU) Parliament, criticizing Pakistan for its proliferation activities, passed a resolution. At the same time, the international media also started to spread rumors that, due to mounting international pressure, Pakistan might halt and roll back its nuclear weapon programme (Mustafa, 2017).

Pakistan is a responsible nuclear state. Pakistan, without compromising on its national security concerns, is playing a responsible role and making every effort to address all these challenges. To ensure a responsible nuclear behavior, Pakistan is taking measures to strengthen its nuclear command and control structure. Pakistan has maintained a strengthened national export control law and regulatory system, and it has taken concrete measures to safeguard its nuclear installations.

Propaganda Campaigns against the Pakistan Army

Pakistan has always faced security challenges from both borders— the Indian and Afghanistan. Pakistan Army has fought three wars with India, followed by the Kargil conflict, insurgencies, and military operations against terrorists. The Army institution of Pakistan has remained the most well-managed, disciplined, and dedicated to the country. Apart from playing a role in the defense of Pakistan's territory, the Army institution also has a remarkable history of making sacrifices and contributions towards nation-building. Pakistan Army, which is considered the backbone support of Pakistan, has been represented very negatively. The adversaries have been blaming the Pakistan Army and Inter-Service Intelligence (ISI) for belligerency in the region and supporting non-state actors. Additionally, India has always blamed the Pakistan Army and ISI for any incident that happens in its region or Indian Occupied Kashmir (IOK). Indeed, India has been trying to divert the world's attention from its atrocities in IOK and subversive activities in Balochistan province of Pakistan (Azad, 2020).

The foreign media has always been prejudiced against Pakistan. It has never applauded and highlighted the sacrifices Pakistan has made in the war against terrorism. The US is targeting Pakistan in collaboration with India and Israel. The Pakistan army has been the strongest obstacle in its way to gain its foreign policy objectives. Hence, they are targeting the Pakistan military from many angles. They are engaged in hybrid warfare in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and are being dragged into the Balochistan turmoil as well. Such attempts to malign prestigious institutions of the state have become a common practice. Negative opinions through the media are overblowing such information, which is leading to misperceptions regarding Pakistan's armed forces and intelligence agencies. However, the Pakistan army and its leading intelligence agency, ISI, have been effectively countering these conspiracies. (ISIS, 2001)

Waging conventional battle against Pakistan remains difficult for the adversaries. Hence, they have launched a propaganda campaign against it. India is trying to build the narrative that she always tried to maintain cordial ties with Pakistan, but its Army does not allow the bilateral relationship to reach a normalized level. Moreover, it is trying to undermine Pakistan's military institution to hide its nefarious designs against Pakistan. It is trying to malign Pakistan on a global level, blaming it for not allowing regional peace and integration. Obviously, India is pursuing the objectives to dismantle the social contract of our country by generating divisions and uncertainty within the country (Malik, 2018).

In fact, the Pakistan Army has successfully tackled lawlessness and effectively fought and defeated insurgencies in Balochistan, and combat terrorism in Ex- Ex-FATA region. Chief of Army Staff General Qamar Javed Bajwa said at the recent Munich Security Conference: The presence of terrorists of various hues and colors cannot be ruled out. However, today, I can say with pride and conviction that there are no organized terrorist camps on our side of the border. Pakistan Army has waged a relentless and bloody fight against terrorism and violent extremism, at a monumental human and material cost. Over 35,000 Pakistanis have lost their lives, over 48,000 are critically wounded or disabled, with a financial cost exceeding US\$250 billion - only a fraction of which is actually shared by our global partners (Malik, 2018). The Pakistan army fully understands the hidden motives and objectives of defamation campaigns launched by India.

It is important to mention that, after the 9/11 incident, Pakistan suffered huge economic losses. In addition to this, it lost about 80,000 human beings, including 5498 military personnel. Moreover, Pakistan deployed 200,000 troops in the Ex-FATA region to eliminate terrorism networks sponsored and nurtured by Indian from across the border.

Indian Hybrid Warfare Strategies against Pakistan

Hybrid warfare has been a preferred strategy for India to achieve its projected goals. Since the formation of its intelligence agency, RAW, it has been constantly involved in subversive activities against Pakistan. Soon after its creation in 1968, the Indian-spy agency started meddling in Pakistan (Stanley, Kokanee, & Hardgrave, 2008). RAW had created a terrorist organization (Mukti Bahini), which was used to exploit the political crisis of Pakistan in the 1970s and eventually resulted in the separation of East Pakistan. It trained, funded, and nurtured the organization that was involved in the act of atrocities against the Pakistan army, their families, and the people of East Pakistan. Since then, it has been actively carrying out covert operations against Pakistan. India has long been involved in covert operations against Pakistan (Dr Farah Naz, 2020).

To achieve its nefarious goals, India has embarked upon a bi-dimensional strategy towards Pakistan. First, it has launched campaigns to diplomatically isolate Pakistan through a blame game of terrorism. Secondly, it is meddling in Pakistan's internal affairs, sponsoring and abetting terrorism. In order to achieve its foreign policy objectives, India has always used a multifaceted approach to undermine Pakistan's position in the global community (Dr. Masood Ur Rehman Khattak, 2019). Indian is trying all means to make Pakistan a diplomatically isolated state in the international community. The Indian-western nexus is behind conspiracies against Pakistan to weaken its position at the global level.

In 2008, former Indian Army chief General (Retired) V.K. Singh established a covert unit in the Indian Army known as the Technical Services Division (TSD) to make Kashmiri leaders loyal and conduct terrorist operations inside Pakistan (International, 2013). Furthermore, the Unit is behind generating subversion in Balochistan. The capture of Indian Spy agent Kulbushan Yadav is clear evidence of Indian covert activities within Pakistani territory. According to General Zubair Mahmood Hayat, "Indian spy agency RAW had established a cell in 2015 dedicated to sabotage CPEC projects in Pakistan. India is involved in the subversive operations in Karachi and Balochistan, which have resulted in the loss of many innocent Pakistanis. The Indian spy, Kulbushan Yadav, and other networks that have been exposed are evidence that they are indeed waging hybrid warfare against Pakistan. It is due to the Indian subversive activities that Pakistan has seen terrorist attacks in Balochistan, Karachi, and in some other areas of the country during the last two decades. (Dawn, Govt airs video of Indian spy admitting involvement in Balochistan insurgency, 2016)

Pursuing its projected goals, India has continued to wage fifth-generation warfare against Pakistan. Ajit Doval, the National Security Advisor (NSA), while describing his approach in dealing with threats to the Indian National Security, said that we deal with the enemy at three levels. First is defensive mode, in which he said we improve our defences at home and deal with it on our own soil. The second mode is defensive offense, in which you have to proactively go to the area from where the threat is coming and neutralize it there. And third is offensive mode, which implies that 'you go for offensive out rightly (Dr. Masood Ur Rehman Khattak, 2019). The doctrine indicates the Indian ambitions of the latest generation of warfare against Pakistan. The latest generation of warfare has already been launched against Pakistan, especially in Balochistan.

Financial Action Task Force: A tool to undermine Pakistan

The Financial Action Task Force (FATF) is an intergovernmental organization that aims to promote policies and standards to eliminate financial crime. Recommendations provided by the organization focus on money laundering,

terrorist financing, and other threats to the financial system of the world. It was formed in the year 1989 at the behest of the G7 and headquartered in Paris. With the emergence of the global economy and global trade, financial crimes such as money laundering are growing (Shahid Karim, 2018).

In the era of hybrid warfare, global organizations are exploited as diplomatic coercion to gain political objectives. Pakistan has made many sacrifices to combat terrorism and ensure peace and security in the region. It played the role of a frontline state in the US-led war against terrorism. Nonetheless, making sacrifices and suffering huge losses in the war against terrorism, the United States has put forward a motion to place its name on a global terrorist-financing watch list.

The Financial Action Task Force (FATF) has placed Pakistan “jurisdictions with strategic deficiencies” known as the grey list of FATF. It is not for the first time that Pakistan's name is on the FATF list; Pakistan was placed on the list in year 2008 2012 to 2015 (Shahid Karim, 2018). Recently, FATF has placed the country's name on the grey list on the grounds that it has structural deficiencies on the count of weak non-compliance with money laundering and terrorism related financing. It is far more political than financial in nature. It has been perceived as an attempt of coercion by the US, with India, a key player at the FATF Asia and the Pacific, to mount pressure on Pakistan to “do more” on terrorism related matters to achieve its political objectives. Enjoying its influence over FATF, the US can make it difficult for Pakistan to be out from the list. The US is a major financier of FATF, and it has more leverage than other states. The US had also cut down its military assistance to Pakistan before placing its name on the FATF list.

India has launched falsified propaganda campaigns against Pakistan to build negative perceptions that Pakistan is sponsoring militancy in the region. It is persistently engaged in generating opportunities for false flag operations such as the attack on the Indian parliament, the Mumbai attack of 2008, the Pathankot attack in 2016, and the Pulwama incident of 2019. The Indian media's negative propaganda campaigns and diplomatic efforts have deeply damaged Pakistan's image at the global level, and as a result of this, Pakistan has been placed on the FATF grey list (Jaffery, 2020). Brigadier (R) Abdul Basit Rana, about FATF, stated that: “India is lobbying with the Financial Action Task Force to discredit Pakistan. If the Indian efforts succeed, it would have a far-reaching effect on Gwadar and CPEC—a game changer for Balochistan and Pakistan in the future” (Rana, 2021).

Indian is making efforts to blacklist Pakistan in the Financial Action Task Force (FATF) and get it labeled as a terror-sponsoring state. In fact, it is another form of economic blackmail to attain strategic objectives. Pakistan's military fully understands the ulterior motives of global defamation campaigns. Pakistan Army and paramilitary forces have successfully tackled

Karachi's lawlessness and successfully fought and defeated insurgencies in Balochistan and the ex-FATA region (Dawn, Pakistan rejects India's 'malicious' statement linking Let leader's conviction with FATF, 2021) . According to the Foreign Office (FO), as for the hypocritical Indian assertions regarding the terror infrastructure and individual terrorists, irrefutable evidence has already been provided by Pakistan to the international community of the active aiding, abetting, planning, promoting, financing, and execution of terrorist activities by India against Pakistan, with impunity. (Dawn, Pakistan rejects India's 'malicious' statement linking Let leader's conviction with FATF, 2021)

Foreign Involvement in Balochistan

Balochistan is a significant geo-strategic location of Pakistan. It has seen insurgencies followed by suicide attacks, bomb blasts, and attacks on infrastructure and security forces throughout history. Foreign hostile forces are sponsoring insurgencies, abetting terrorism, sabotaging development projects, and publishing misleading and fake media reports to influence the minds of local communities and incite them against their own state and its institutions. Anti-Pakistan forces have been meddling in the province for a long time. Russia, the US, India, Israel, the UK, Afghanistan, and Iran have been part of conspiracies against the province (Muhammad Waqas Haider, 2020). They have been trying to incite the locals against their own state and its institutions, sponsoring insurgencies and promoting propaganda.

The world powers always tried to promote their interest in Balochistan to exploit the region as a tool to make Pakistan a destabilized country. Russia had supported the "Greater Balochistan" movement. When the Soviet Union invaded Afghanistan in 1979, it was believed that it would also try to take possession of Balochistan's deep-sea-water port, and the Baloch insurgents and their militant activities would be helpful to its attempt. After gaining control of Afghan territory, Russia tried hard to convince the Baloch to revolt against Pakistan's central government. The Soviets assured Baloch that they would be given autonomy over the province. The Soviets were pursuing the objective to maintain domination in Kabul as their base and to raise the issue of 'Greater Balochistan' from the land of Afghanistan, and make an attempt to separate Balochistan from the state of Pakistan (Carson, 2018).

At present, Balochistan is being subjected to fifth-generation warfare massively. Anti-Pakistan forces are pursuing their political goals to generate lawlessness and uncertainty in the province to destabilize Pakistan. India, through Iran and Afghanistan, is conducting covert operations in Balochistan. India is engaged in subversive activities in the province on a massive level. India has established consulates in different cities of Afghanistan, which are being used to conduct terrorism in Balochistan. The

Iranian and Afghan territories have become a haven for the Indian-sponsored terrorists. The capture of Indian spy agent Kulbushan Jadav in 2016 confirmed the Indian involvement in Balochistan through Iran and Afghanistan (Dawn, 2016) . The Indian intelligence agency RAW and the Afghan NDS have joined hands and are engaged in subversive activities in Balochistan. The enemies are indeed pursuing their objectives to destabilize Pakistan and damage its national unity. Additionally, India has launched media campaigns by using all means, including television, newspapers, social media, films, dramas, and radio, to promote its falsified propaganda against Pakistan, focusing on Balochistan province. India has launched a multimedia website and app of the Balochi radio service, which broadcasts its transmission in the Balochi language, airing statements of the senior officials of the Indian Intelligence agency, RAW, to incite the Balochi community to stand up against Pakistan. Besides, Indian has also launched a TV news Channel “Zee Salam” with the same purpose (Maqbool, 2018).

Way Forward

The West-Indian nexus has deeply affected Pakistan, and it has pushed the country toward a difficult position. However, Pakistan has all the strength and capability to counter the challenges of hybrid warfare. In order to make its counter strategy more effective, Pakistan needs a comprehensive counter strategy that includes all the stakeholders at the federal and provincial levels. At present, we are at war. The adversaries are targeting our country with hybrid warfare. They are trying to divide Pakistani society based on ethnicity and sectarianism. Pakistan should take measures to counter these conspiracies. The government should take steps to overcome the sectarian and ethnic issues and save the society from further division. Most of the domestic issues Pakistan is presently facing are due to the lack of Good Governance. Ensuring good governance is an urgent need of the time to address the genuine reservations of the people (Muhammad Waqas Haider, 2020) . Pakistan should improve its governance and counter propaganda campaigns launched against it by foreign forces. Education is considered a weapon of social change and national development. Pakistan should start technical education, create and groom skills. Steps should be taken to ensure a uniform education system for all in terms of the National curriculum. This will provide equal opportunities for upward social mobility. Pakistan needs a comprehensive counter-strategy to counter the challenges of hybrid warfare. The media plays a crucial role in representing a state in the international community. In Pakistan, there is presently no policy-based discussion between the media and the government, and Pakistan also lacks enough English news channels to portray the positive image of the country at the global level. Pakistani society should collectively respond to hybrid

warfare; the media, the civil society, and academia should play a role in the national unity of the country.

Conclusion

The study discussed the challenges of fifth-generation warfare to Pakistan. The geographical location of Pakistan makes it one of the important locations in the world. The global powers have always meddled in the internal affairs of Pakistan. Pakistan has witnessed wars, conflicts, insurgencies, terrorist attacks, bomb blasts, and other acts of terrorism in its history. Since Pakistan became a nuclear power in 1998, direct military confrontation has become impossible for the adversaries. Hence, the adversaries are targeting Pakistan with soft power approaches, supporting insurgencies, giving rise to ethnic and sectarian conflicts, and launching media campaigns based on false news and misleading reports. In the realm of latest generation warfare, media, along with the internet, is playing a crucial role. Currently, Pakistan is facing fifth-generation warfare waged by hostile intelligence agencies against it.

Pakistan is facing the threat of hybrid warfare from many fronts. Adversaries are trying to exploit domestic fissures. The population of Pakistan is constituted by different communities with distinct cultures. The adversaries are trying to create differences among these communities to undermine the national unity of Pakistan. For instance, India is trying to create a trust gap between the local communities and the state. India is using Iranian and Afghan soil against Pakistan. The RAW-NDS nexus is targeting Pakistan with hybrid warfare. In addition, India has joined hands with its western allies to conduct subversive activities in Pakistan, particularly targeting Balochistan, Karachi, and the Ex-FATA region in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province. India is sponsoring terrorist organizations in Balochistan to create lawlessness and chaos in the province and destabilize the whole country. Besides, India has launched media campaigns highlighting fake news and misleading reports about Balochistan. The enemies are trying to create a gap between the people and the state and incite them against their own state and institution. This is indeed an attempt by enemies to fuel domestic fissures and damage Pakistan's national unity.

Falsified propaganda campaigns have damaged Pakistan's image in the international community. The adversaries have given rise to a narrative that Pakistan is an unsafe country, religiously intolerant, a "haven" for terrorists, and that the nuclear weapons of Pakistan could fall into the hands of terrorists. At present, Pakistan is on the FATF's grey list, which is indeed the result of Indian negative propaganda campaigns and false flag operations. In fact, Pakistan played a crucial role and made many sacrifices during the war on terror, but it did not receive the due acknowledgement, and its role

was never appreciated and is still being told to “do more”. Pakistan needs an effective counter-strategy to counter the challenges of fifth-generation warfare.

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